

Emerging Trends Of Commerce And Management Education On Significant Revitalization And Contemporary Issues In Indian Context

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Abstract:

For all students, studying business and management has been inspiring. This has opened up a wide range of options for those interested in careers in business and management. In the last 20 years, there have been numerous innovations and paradigm shifts. Education in business and management is a growing area in India's educational system. Since 1991, when globalization, privatization, and other changes took hold, the roles of management and commerce have expanded. Additionally, commerce and management education has been widely offered to develop new eras and dimensions in the corresponding fields while creating new opportunities for masters. Since then, society and everyday life have undergone significant changes. We have evolved hundreds of times faster thanks to education, and everything has changed significantly, including morals, ethics, and significance. The same is true of educational traditions and patterns. The most significant gaps in management education in India are highlighted here, along with what needs to be done to create successful trends. Most significantly, the introduction of commerce and management education has altered the entire situation and redefined the terms and benchmarks. Students today are urged to recognize their ability to succeed in any field they feel drawn to. The sky is the only limit, and the world is at your disposal. A vital commerce education accelerates any nation or region's socioeconomic development. It gives the information needed to meet the needs of today's very competitive business world. It aids youth in determining the best course of action for their survival and development. The rate at which commerce education is growing in this field is clear from the fact that it is becoming increasingly popular as a way to gain knowledge, improve skills, make money, and be creative, all of which are important for a country's economic growth. This research paper looks at the state of commerce education in India, focusing on significant problems, essential government programs, and ideas for bringing the field back to life.

Keywords: Emerging trends, revitalization, commerce education, economic prosperity, key challenges

Introduction:

The field of business and management education has expanded significantly and now encompasses a wide range of viewpoints. The future of management education in India is being shaped by deans, deans of business schools, students, business advisory councils, administrative staff, and recruiters of graduates. In this scenario, there will be topics of interest to each group. As the country's businesses continue to expand, there is a significant need for top-notch managers in India. That business and management are worthwhile ideas that guarantee a quick return on investment. With increasing industry demand, commerce and management education has seen significant growth over the past few years. Education in business and management is in high demand, particularly in light of recent liberalization, privatization, and globalization trends. As a result, there are a number of challenges in business management education that call for the integration of management education with the corporate sector, an upgrade in

curriculum and course content, the design of various executive programs, the upkeep of an effective regulatory system to prevent mushrooming, and a focus on research. India has a great deal of potential to advance the development of a knowledge society. The recent expansion of the Indian economy and the need to maintain it are also pressuring the Indian government to speed up the development of all components of the Indian educational system. Education in business and management plays a significant role in 21st-century economic development as well as in the world's top educational systems. Every year, thousands of aspirants attempt to enroll in management programs. To draw candidates for industry-integrated programs, a management degree and the issues of employability and experience learning are continually promoted. Today's business environment is unpredictable due to the Indian economy's rapid growth and an increase in cross-border deals. As a result, employers now have higher standards than ever before. They are seeking young people with experience, tact, and management

skills. There isn't a single, widely accepted definition of e-business or e-commerce. As a result, it is important to define terms and define the context in which they are used. Three key stakeholders are impacted by e-commerce: society, businesses, and consumers. There are several benefits, including reduced costs, improved efficiency, customization, and access to international markets. Additionally, e-commerce has drawbacks that affect all of the stakeholders. It's crucial to recognize the various terms used in electronic commerce and to analyze their definitions and usage in order to comprehend it. These include information overload, issues with reliability and security, cost of access, social divides, and challenges with Internet policing.

Understanding the limitations and minimizing the negative effects while maximizing the positive effects are essential to successful e-commerce. Businesses that engage in e-commerce typically use some or all of the following strategies:

Give information about the virtual storefront on websites that have online catalogs, which are occasionally gathered into a "virtual mall"

On online markets, buy or sell.

Through web contacts and social media, collect and use demographic data.

Use electronic data interchange to exchange data between businesses.

Send emails or faxes to existing and potential clients (for example, with newsletters).

Use buying and selling between businesses.

Secure business transactions are offered.

Participate in retail to introduce new goods and services

So what is E-Commerce?

Electronic commerce, also referred to as E-commerce, is the exchange of goods and services over computer networks like the Internet. Mobile commerce, electronic funds transfers, supply chain management, Internet marketing, online transaction processing, electronic data interchange (EDI), inventory management systems, and automated data collection systems are just a few of the technologies that are used in electronic commerce. Although it may also use other technologies like e-mail, modern electronic commerce typically uses the World Wide Web for at least one phase of the transaction's life cycle. The simplest definition of it is conducting business

transactions electronically. The following is how the European Commission defined e-commerce in 1977: According to the April 1997 issue of ERCIM News (No. 29), "Europe has lagged behind the rest of the world in its transition to the information society." There is significant activity emerging in the area of electronic commerce, and a distinct European focus is undoubtedly emerging. This is happening on three fronts: first, many European nations, including France, the Netherlands, Sweden, and the UK, are seriously utilizing electronic commerce; second, these national activities are being brought together through a new user organization, Electronic Commerce Europe (ECE); third, the European Commission is bringing its various actions under a cooperative umbrella and urging serious implementation initiatives under the most recent ESPRIT Theme. Data processing underpins electronic commerce, including text, sound, and image. The company engages in a variety of activities, including the exchange of goods and services electronically, the instant delivery of digital content, business plans, team-based design and engineering, electronic stock trading, government contracting, direct marketing, and post-sale services. E-commerce is defined as the exchange of goods and services, the sending of money or data over an electronic network, most notably the Internet. These commercial transactions can take place between businesses, consumers, businesses, or consumers and businesses. E-business and e-commerce are frequently used interchangeably.

Impact of e-commerce on markets and retailers:

As consumers' access to information about products and prices increases thanks to e-commerce, economists predict that price competition will become more intense. According to research conducted by four economists at the University of Chicago, the growth of online shopping has also had an impact on the industry structure of two sectors that have experienced significant e-commerce growth: book stores and travel agencies. Larger businesses are typically able to take advantage of economies of scale and provide lower prices. The very smallest category of booksellers—stores with fewer than four employees—has been the lone exception to this trend, and they seem to

have withstood it. Buyers and sellers who engage in online commerce rely on technology that is based on the Internet to complete their transactions. E-commerce is well known for enabling business communication and transaction formation anytime and anywhere. Business can be done on the internet whether a person is in the US or abroad. Geophysical barriers can be overcome thanks to the power of e-commerce, making all consumers and companies on the planet potential clients and suppliers.

Benefits of e-commerce:

E-commerce has many advantages, including quick access, a larger selection of goods and services, accessibility, and global reach. Its perceived drawbacks include occasionally poor customer service, the inability to physically touch or see a product before making a purchase, and the required wait period for product shipping. Businesses should authenticate business transactions, restrict access to resources like WebPages for registered or chosen users, encrypt communications, and implement security technologies like the Secure Sockets Layer to ensure the security, privacy, and effectiveness of e-commerce.

Benefits of e-commerce to organizations:

E-commerce offers a number of benefits, such as quick access, a wide range of products and services, accessibility, and a global presence. The occasional unsatisfactory customer service, the inability to physically touch or see a product before making a purchase, and the required wait time for product shipping are some of its alleged disadvantages. To ensure the security, privacy, and efficiency of e-commerce, businesses should authenticate business transactions, restrict access to resources like WebPages for registered or chosen users, encrypt communications, and implement security technologies like the Secure Sockets Layer.

Benefits of e-commerce to customers:

E-commerce offers customers a number of advantages, including the ability to conduct business from almost anywhere, 24 hours a day, 365 days a year; more options; access to lower-priced goods and services due to the ability to compare prices quickly and easily; in some cases, quick delivery of goods and services, particularly for digitized goods; and the ability to receive relevant and detailed information.

Benefits of e-commerce to society:

Finally, e-commerce can have positive effects on society by allowing more people to work from home and travel less for shopping, which reduces traffic and air pollution, enables some goods to be sold at lower prices benefiting the poor, allows individuals in Third World countries and rural areas to enjoy products and services that would otherwise not be available to them, facilitates public service delivery at a lower cost, and so on.

Review of Literature:

Growth & Globalization of Indian Management Education-Issues & Solutions-

(Dr. Reddy Irala Lokanandha, 2006) the authors have granted the designation of Indian B schools, which could pass the rigorous examination of good instruction. The Indian B schools must take numerous measures to meet the problems, and the associated colleges must exercise greater financial and academic autonomy. The autonomous institutions must also improve their curricula. Admission Criteria as a Predictor of Academic Performance in a Management Programme

(Dr. Lokanandha Reddy Irala, 2006) they emphasize on Indian B-Schools in their study paper and set very strict entry requirements for their Management programs. Writing test, group discussion, and personal interview are the three evaluation criteria that are typically used to select the top students for management schools.

(K. Vidyakala, 2009) in their research article on Talent Acquisition and the Role of Management Education in India opine that it has become vital for every organization to attract and retain the best available talent but worldwide organizations are subjected to heavy pressure due to the declining supply of talent. The demand for talented people exceeds the supply of skilled workers which has been fulfilled by management education.

Major objectives of the present study:

1. To explore the changes towards commerce and management education in India.
2. To be made aware about the current scenarios with direct exposure to industrial affairs in their students.
3. To know the contemporary issues in the field of commerce and management education.
4. To provide the better prospects for the students in commerce and management education

Perspective change in the Content and Process of Commerce and Management Education:

The traditional methods of the educational pattern have transformed the way that business and management education is taught. In the modern period, commerce has changed dramatically from being limited to manually handled accounting-related procedures. new ideas and technologies The emphasis of all commerce and management education has changed due to new learning, new teaching tools, and new industry trends. As a result, graduates in these fields are now expected to manage all corporate activities. They hold high positions in organizations and contribute to every important area of the business and the sector; as a result, teaching methodologies all over the world have seen a considerable change with the introduction of contemporary tools, procedures, and approaches. Education in business and management must now create student- and job-centered programs that prepare students to meet industry demands for knowledge, competencies, and abilities. To meet the demands of the global viewpoints of business and management education, we must work in this direction to create new perspectives in the field of commerce and management education.

Contemporary issues in commerce and management education:

As the educational landscape has completely transformed, schools are now awarding degrees to students who are ill-equipped to find employment in their fields of study. As the subject is already in demand from both institutions and students, now is the moment to reassess the education in commerce and management and to develop new areas for the discipline. The university should implement remedial measures by establishing new courses, new syllabuses, and reorganizing existing course curricula to meet industry need. We must first identify the areas from the perspective of the industry. The key topics that need to be covered in business and management education are mentioned in this article. Contemporary issues in commerce and management are the following:

Management science:- Knowledge management for all industries, including petroleum and mining management,

corporate governance, business ethics, and business education

Spirituality and management:- Indian ethos and values, value management, meditation and management of stress, yoga in management

Marketing:- Social marketing, environmental marketing, green marketing, integrated marketing communications, marketing analytics, consumerism in the digital age, and branding in cyberspace.

Human resource management:- Organizational effectiveness, competence mapping, human resource information systems, human resource audits, human capital management, talent management, image management, image management, HR analytics, strategic HRM, and green organizational behavior.

Banking, Financial and accounting:- Monetary analysis investing and banking, financial market, taxation and auditing, Cost and work accountants, cost management accountants, and company secretaries Actuary, financial advisor Asset management, commercial banking, equity researcher, investment banking business financing risk control, Stock trading, forensic accounting, technologically-enhanced banking, and financial reporting

Information technology: - Electronic marketing, Business intelligence and analytics, Skill management, Banking with technology, Digital marketing, E-commerce, Mobile commerce.

General Management:- Management of tourism and hospitality, packaging, waste, crowdsourcing, creativity, leadership, productivity, and performance, as well as management of the treasury, health care, and maintenance.

Significant challenges for commerce and management education in present context:

Emerging issue in global Economy, Commerce and Management.

Internationalization of Financial Market in the World.

Role of Foreign Direct Investment and Foreign Institutional Investment.

Reform in Indian and International Economic Sectors.

Challenges and Strategies for export and import of Trade, Commerce and Industries in global scenario.

Job oriented course and programs to be identified with understanding the career prospects.

Maintaining the industry –institute interface to generate employment and learning.

Major thrust areas in commerce and management as well as emerging challenges:

Faculty Development opportunities and management development programmes

Development of Teaching Material and Case Studies.

Post-experience and Distance Learning Programmes

Institution-Industry Linkage.

Restructuring of the Existing P. G. Management Programmes.

International Cooperation and Collaboration for Export of Management Education.

Quality and Excellence.

Introduction of Assessment and Accreditation Procedures.

Placement and career opportunities.

Findings and significant analysis of study conducted:

The study has considered the Competency development approach of selected top Indian B-schools in terms of the following parameters:

Curriculum of PGDM /MBA Programme

Industry integrated programme

International Internship

Faculty exchange program

Dual degree programs

Campuses aboard and student exchange programmes

Overcoming challenges for major thrust areas in commerce and management education:

Re-modelling and designing of commerce management education.

Developing professionalism in higher education sector

Competency based salary structure to attract the efficient teaching professionals.

Focus over the job centered programs, vocational programs and programs satisfying the industry requirements

Industry officials, executives should be the member of the education system to evaluate the feasibility of the program

Development of individual's mindset and attitude towards the teaching profession

Industry –institute interface should be developed or there should be a linkage

between industry and institute to learn practical knowledge and exposure.

The project work should be contextual, relevant and should focus on the current scenarios.

Make accreditation mandatory to ensure quality of education.

Use online courses and other e-learning methods to increase training opportunities for field and local staff

Provide training in languages besides English and ensure that training is provided even in emergency situations.

Suggestions and Recommendations:

Restructuring the syllabi at UG and PG levels. Apart from the subject knowledge, soft skills like good writing skills, listening skills, presentation skills, interpersonal skills, leadership crisis management skills, problem solving skills etc., Must be made compulsory in view of its importance in the contemporary job market.

Provide facilities for industrial visits. Arrange Guest lecturers from expert academicians and industry experienced people.

A detailed industry visit report based on the field visits should be made an integral part of the course.

Redesigning the teaching methods, as a deviation from traditional teaching methods

The management colleges / schools are able to use innovative and practical teaching methods like management games, workshops and seminars, Mock interviews, proper presentations, individual assignments, field surveys and case studies etc.,

Control the study centers, UGC will take care of these centers, in some areas these centers are follow malpractices in examinations.

Work with agencies to design educational and training programs that meet the needs of the agencies

Develop multi-disciplinary curricula to prepare students for careers in humanitarian work

Encourage faculty and student exchanges

Consider establishing an academic association of humanitarian studies and/or a dedicated journal

Conclusion:

The education system for commerce and management in India needs to be reviewed right away because it has been cited as having the best job prospects. This education system has value in both the public and

private sectors, and it has made significant contributions to the growth of small businesses, startups, and other ventures. Now is the moment to analyze current market trends and industry demand, and universities should create their course curricula in accordance with the trends. Industry-institute interaction is necessary to create jobs in this industry. The global curriculum needs to be developed by Indian B-schools in a more rigorous and planned manner in order to foster students' development of true global competency. Along with core courses, more global and international courses should be included to each and every speciality. The teachers must be of the highest caliber, having exposure to other countries and a range of industrial experience. The issue for today's management schools is to prepare their students for the needs of business. Due to a number of obstacles they are unable to overcome, colleges and management institutes are unable to establish quality benchmarks. They struggle with political meddling, budgetary limitations, and academic restrictions. Therefore, these institutions permit some autonomy since it is necessary to meet these obstacles and use the necessary abilities. This is done in the goal of providing high-quality education. Therefore, these institutions must be strict and regulated; otherwise, they will start to resemble other degree programs offered by universities and colleges at the state and federal levels. Cost reductions, improved efficiency, and personalization are benefits of e-commerce. It's crucial to recognize the many phrases used in electronic commerce and to analyze their definitions and usage in order to comprehend it. Understanding the restrictions and reducing the negative effects are essential for successful online business.

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